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D 7.2 Detailed engagement plan for new users' communities

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0. Abstract

This Deliverable, D7.2, is part of Work Package 7 “Training and Engagement” which aims to expand the service portfolio and widen service coverage for new user communities. The new user communities include the fields of social sciences and humanities; built heritage; palaeontology and palaeoanthropology; and archaeology. These are widely varying and disparate groups, with different types of internal organisation and different degrees of coordination as well as different levels of engagement with scientific research. Here, we propose a plan for engagement with new communities. Some strategies are common to the four new user communities. This maximises effectiveness and impact, and minimises duplication. It will also allow us to easily extend our strategy to any further future new user groups. However, we recognise that the differences between the groups mean that we will need flexible strategies that take into account these dissimilarities. In all cases, we recognise the importance of two-way dialogue to seek the opinions of members of the user groups and the need to adjust IPERION HS’s offering to take account of the needs of the different groups.

We propose to monitor engagement of members of the different groups as they request Trans-National Access and calculate Key Performance Indicators that will allow us to monitor the engagement of new user communities compared to more established users.

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3. Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Expansion
AAH	Association for Art History
AAMC	Association of Art Museum Curators
AEA	Association for Environmental Archaeology
AIC	American Institute for Conservation
BAM	Federal Institute for Materials Testing (<i>Bundesanstalt für Materialforschung und -prüfung</i>)
BINDT	The British Institute of Non-Destructive Testing
CAA	College Art Association
CAAH	Consortium for Art and Architectural Historians
CCI	Canadian Conservation Institute
CHN	Climate Heritage Network
CIfA	Chartered Institute for Archaeologists
CIHA	Comité International d'Histoire de l'Art
CCI	Canadian Conservation Institute
DNK	Deutsches Nationalkomitee für Denkmalschutz
DGZfP	German Society for Non-Destructive Testing (<i>Deutsche Gesellschaft für Zerstörungsfreie Prüfung</i>)
EAA	European Association of Archaeologists
EAC	European Archaeology Council
E.C.C.O.	European Confederation of Conservators-Restorers' Organisations
EEHB	Energy Efficiency in Historic Building
EFCC	European Federation for Construction Chemicals
EFNDT	European Federation for Non-Destructive Testing
EMU	European Mineralogical Union
ENCORE	European Network for Conservation-Restoration Education
E-RIHS	European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
ESHE	European Society for the Study of Human Evolution
EURBICA	European Branch of the International Council on Archives
EUROROC	European Federation of Natural Stone Industries
GCI	Getty Conservation Institute
GRI	Getty Research Institute
HS	Heritage Science
ICCROM	International Centre for the Study of the Preservation and Restoration of Cultural Property
ICOM	International Council of Museums
ICOM-CC	International Council of Museums – Committee for Conservation
ICOMOS	International Council on Monuments and Sites and various Scientific Committees such as CIPA, ISCS, ISCARSAH, ISCEAH etc.
ICON	The Institute of Conservation
IIC	International Institute for Conservation

IfS	Institut für Steinkonservierung
IMC	International Medieval Congress
IMLS	Institute of Museum and Library Services
IPERION HS	Integrating Platforms for the European Research Infrastructure ON Heritage Science
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
NEMO	Network of European Museum Organisations
NFDI	Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur
PALASS	Palaeontological Association
PPA	Palaeopathology Association
PS	The Prehistoric Society
RS	The Roman Society
RSA	Renaissance Society of America
SAS	Society of Archaeological Sciences
STBA	Sustainable Traditional Buildings Alliance
TCDA	Trapped Charge Dating Association
UISPP	Union of Prehistoric and Protohistoric Sciences
VDR	Union of (German) Restorers (<i>Verband der Restauratoren</i>)
WTA	Wissenschaftlich-Technische Arbeitsgemeinschaft für Bauwerkserhaltung und Denkmalpflege

4. Introduction

This Deliverable D7.2 is part of IPERION HS Workpackage 7 (Training and Engagement). WP7 aims to engage users at all stages of their journey through IPERION HS and in this Deliverable, we are particularly concerned with supporting users from groups who have not previously engaged with the E-RIHS community. The specific new groups we aim to engage with are (i) Social Sciences and Humanities (Task 7.3); (ii) Built Environment (T7.4); (iii) Palaeoanthropology and Palaeontology (T7.5); and (iv) Archaeology (T7.6).

These are disparate groups, with different levels of coordination and integration, some of which have existing communities and some of which are made up of multiple interacting communities. The engagement with research infrastructures varies considerably both between these groups and within them. The optimum mechanism for interacting with these communities is different for the different communities and needs to be targeted carefully and sensitively.

This deliverable document describes the development of a comprehensive strategy for engagement with these new user communities. We expect that the processes of engagement will change through the lifetime of IPERION HS as we learn more about the communities and they learn more about the benefits that access to research infrastructure can offer.

5. Strategy for engagement with new communities

We recognise that these user communities are different from each other, and that in some cases there are diverse groups within the communities that require specific and targeted engagement strategies. However, as much as possible, we will develop common engagement methods. This will simplify our message, minimise duplication of efforts and will also mean that if we expand to include additional new user communities, we can modify the existing strategy rather than develop a new one.

Here, we list strategies that we anticipate will be common across multiple user groups. In sections 6-9, we describe in detail how we intend to engage with specific groups.

Our over-arching principle is not to be prescriptive. We want to enter into dialogue with user groups rather than didactically telling them what we have to offer. We hope that this collaborative approach will have a number of advantages. It will help to ensure that our offer is relevant to the different communities, and that we present our infrastructures to them appropriately. We expect to identify research infrastructure facilities that are currently still missing from IPERION HS. This will inform WP6 especially T6.2 (sustainability) which is developing a strategy for the sustainability of the future Research Infrastructure. This would be extremely difficult without ongoing dialogue with representatives of the new communities. Importantly, we need to learn how we can best talk through and develop research questions with users so that both we and they understand the questions posed, and can co-create potential solutions. We will update our Engagement Plan as new users help us to design and refine the best engagement strategies.

For all communities, identifying the most appropriate contacts is of fundamental importance for the success of future engagement. These contacts will vary between communities but are likely to include policymakers as well as scientists and heritage professionals and practitioners.

There is a wide range of communication tools that are common across academic disciplines. The use of many of these have accelerated as a result of the Covid pandemic. We expect to exploit the full range of electronic communication media to facilitate two-way dialogue, including

- social media (IPERION HS's Twitter, LinkedIn, YouTube and Facebook channels)
- the webinar series that will be developed as part of T7.2
- online events
- e-mail lists (*Global Conservation Forum*, former *Conservation DistList* etc.)
- media interviews (press, TV)
- newsletters including e-newsletters and bulletins
- scientific and professional journals.

We recognise that not all members of the new user communities will benefit from institutional subscriptions to journals and libraries. All peer-reviewed scientific publications resulting from IPERION HS funding must be open access (free of charge online for any user) according to Article 29 of the Grant Agreement and the EU's Open Science Policy¹, and we will ensure that all other outputs are freely available.

We will work with Task 7.2 (user forum) to ensure that information is disseminated through user groups, and also collaborate with the producers of the webinar series that is proposed. The first set of eight webinars introducing the facilities that IPERION HS can offer is intended to include an introduction to IPERION HS suitable for new users and descriptions of the three platforms, with case studies, as well as four webinars, one led by each of the leaders of T7.3-6, which will be aimed at each of the four new user communities. We will work closely with WP8 (communication) and the helpdesk to ensure that any communication from IPERION HS is appropriate for new user communities, and that any queries raised by members of these communities are identified and addressed. In time, it is also expected that the webinars will showcase case studies specifically by end-users from the new communities, which will promote the use of IPERION facilities within these communities.

There are some key individuals and institutions that are important contacts in multiple communities. It is important that communications with these is coordinated and streamlined. For this reason, all activities aimed at engaging new user groups will be sent by the relevant leaders of T7.3-6 task leaders copying in the Central Office (T8.3), who will coordinate communication and promotion activities at Project level.

¹ https://ec.europa.eu/info/research-and-innovation/strategy/goals-research-and-innovation-policy/open-science_en

6. Social Sciences and Humanities Community

Purpose

Some of the communities of museum curators, archivists, conservators, heritage managers, palaeographers, codicologists, art historians, historians, social scientists and other heritage scholars and professionals closely engage with the heritage science community; however, there is a continuous need to strongly engage specifically with these groups of our potential user community. On the one hand, this is because of the specific skills and expertise that can be brought on board (e.g. in conservation), but on the other hand, this is because of the lack of awareness on how scientific training, expertise and methodologies can help them in their specific needs and questions, a potential that can be enabled by IPERION HS. There is therefore a need to engage with training activities for the access providers as well as for the users, as well as a pressing need to directly involve these communities as well as disseminate the information about IPERION HS.

Characteristics of the communities

The SSH communities are diverse in interest and level of prior engagement. They are usually very specialised, and although multi-disciplinarity is present, it tends to be nuanced. In many cases these professionals may not have had prior exposure to research infrastructures, but are well aware that scientific knowledge can be a formidable tool. However, they may not be quite sure how best to engage with science and the scientists. In spite of this, they often have very clear ideas where the gaps in their fields lie, although they may not immediately think of/know of potential scientific solutions. Furthermore, these specialists bring the essential knowledge about heritage management and interpretation that heritage scientists benefit from, offering the potential for a two-way learning process.

We particularly note the community of conservators, as conservation training nowadays usually includes science elements, which are usually lacking in the academic background of museum curators, archivists, etc. Indeed, IPERION CH did focus on conservators, providing a model by which engagement with these communities might be developed.

General needs

Two-way communication is needed to determine what the community needs and ensure they have sufficient help and understanding to be able to engage with IPERION HS.

Professional bodies include the International Institute for Conservation (IIC), the International Council of Museums – Committee for Conservation (ICOM-CC), the International Council on Monuments and Sites (ICOMOS) and its various National and Scientific Committees, the Association of Art Museum Curators (AAMC), the Consortium for Art and Architectural Historians (CAAH) and other relevant bodies. These will be contacted through local experts and other colleagues who are members of these bodies, to facilitate introductions and to promote informal discussions as well as work towards jointly organised sessions at their events and conferences, and thus encourage a better understanding of the IPERION HS capacity and community. Another contact node can be International Centre for the Study of the Preservation and Restoration of Cultural Property (ICCROM), an Intergovernmental Organization based in Rome, Italy, which is connected to IPERION HS through colleagues who had been serving on the ICCROM Council and other project activities.

This will help identify needs and lead to engagement with IPERION HS. In particular, we note the forthcoming ICCROM workshop on ARCHLABs² which involves IPERION HS and which will directly involve end users in the development of management protocols for heritage reference collections.

Strategies for engagement

STEP 1: Identify National and International Key Experts in the target areas who can then facilitate contact with Key players in the various organisations we wish to engage with.

STEP 2: Engage with the identified Key players and Start a Dialogue - small groups consisting of us, key expert/s and their international contact/s

STEP 3: Identify the Key Areas/Questions to 'Answer' – using the information from STEP 2, identify the ways in which we can collaborate with the community based on their needs and/or the queries they have.

STEP 4: Compile a Report on the Results

STEP 5: Decide via which Media/Method to Transfer the Information (based on Steps 3 and 4) - this can range from presenting a paper at identified international conference/s, webinars or more interactive options.

The task will result in a report on social sciences and humanities community research needs that could be addressed using heritage science research facilities (D7.6). Data for this report will be generated from the activities described above as well as interviews and/or questionnaires with stakeholders.

² <https://www.iccrom.org/news/international-workshop-heritage-samples-archives-call-partners>

Table 1 Potential institutions to be addressed within T7.3 (*Social Sciences and Humanities*) – initially the European and International organisations will be targeted before American and Canadian ones

Association for Art History	AAH	https://forarthistory.org.uk/
Association of Art Museum Curators	AAMC	https://www.artcurators.org/
American Institute for Conservation	AIC	https://www.culturalheritage.org
College Art Association (USA)	CAA	https://www.collegeart.org
Association for Art History (UK)	CAAH	https://forarthistory.org.uk
Canadian Conservation Institute	CCI	https://www.canada.ca/en/conservation-institute.html
Caravaggio Foundation		https://www.caravaggio-foundation.org
Comité International d'Histoire de l'Art	CIHA	http://www.ciha.org/
Deutscher Museumsbund	DMB	https://www.museumsbund.de/
European Confederation of Conservator-Restorers' Organisations	ECCO	http://www.ecco-eu.org
European Network for Conservation-Restoration Education	ENCORE	http://www.encore-edu.org/
European Branch of the International Council on Archives	EURBICA	https://www.ica.org/en/about-eurbica
Getty Conservation Institute	GCI	https://www.getty.edu/conservation
Getty Research Institute	GRI	https://www.getty.edu/research/
International Centre for the Study of the Preservation and Restoration of Cultural Property	ICCROM	https://www.iccrom.org
International Council of Museums	ICOM	https://icom.museum/en/
International Council of Museums _ Committee for Conservation	ICOM-CC	http://www.icom-cc.org/
The Institute of Conservation (UK)	ICON	https://icon.org.uk
International Institute for Conservation	IIC	https://www.iiconservation.org
Institute of Museum and Library Services	IMLS	https://www.imls.gov/
Andrew W Mellon Foundation	MELLON	https://mellon.org/
National Endowment for the Arts	NEA	https://www.arts.gov/
Network of European Museum Organisations	NEMO	https://www.ne-mo.org
The Renaissance Society of America (USA)	RSA	https://www.rsa.org
Schweizerisches Institut für Kunstwissenschaft	SIK-ISEA	https://www.sik-isea.ch/de-ch/
Union of (German) Restorers (<i>Verband der Restauratoren</i>)	VDR	

7. Built Environment Community

Purpose

The heritage built environment represents an important new community for the IPERION HS project and thus increased engagement will be necessary in order to develop a user base of building surveyors, facility managers, building managers, construction engineers, building conservators and building physicists, but also climate scientists to show possibilities and potentials to this user community. This engagement is necessary as a contribution of the heritage sector to the currently most ambitious project of the European Union, the “Green Deal” to adapt and mitigate climate change impacts. Furthermore, it will help to raise visibility and awareness about the significant contributions the built environment and respective conservation efforts can make to successfully implement the Green Deal.

Many actors in the built environment may not be aware of the possibilities provided by ARCHLAB, FIXLAB or MOLAB platforms to answer questions about the history of buildings, traditional building technology or art technology of building elements like wall paintings or other decorative elements as well as modern buildings from the 20th century with a plurality of new materials and components. However, both from an architectural historic point of view and more importantly regarding questions of sustainable renovation and energetic refurbishment of historic buildings, detailed and state of the art analyses are a prerequisite for achieving sustainable protection, renovation, restoration and preservation measures, and will support assessing heritage values and societal impact.

Characteristics of the communities

The built heritage community is very fragmented comprising many different disciplines from architects, craft companies, conservators/restorers in public and private institutions. Conservators or restorers with a university background may know certain analytical methods but may not be aware of IPERION HS.

Especially craftspeople will be interested in learning more about new analytical tools in order to assess and understand better historic and traditional technologies and to better tailor conservation measures. Often a more in depth information is needed and knowledge about the new high tech instrumentation for analytics is missing and not well understood. Here support is needed to reach this target group.

General needs

Communication has to be enhanced to better inform the built heritage sector about what IPERION can offer. In a second step discussions about the needs to ensure they have sufficient support and understanding to be able to engage with IPERION HS.

Training and education workshops in the new analytical methods should enhance necessary skills and can contribute to achieve a more sustainable renovation/restoration/preservation of built heritage.

“Translators” can facilitate access for craftsmen helping them with formulating suitable questions and selecting the appropriate methods to find solutions, and hopefully co-create new research questions and projects

Strategies for engagement

STEP 1: Identify National and International Key Experts in the target areas who can then facilitate contact with Key players in the various organisations we wish to engage with.

STEP 2: Engage with the identified Key players and Start a Dialogue - small groups consisting of the IPERION team with key experts and their international contacts

STEP 3: Identify the Key Areas/Questions to 'Answer' – using the information from STEP 2, identify the ways in which we can target the audience based on the help they require and/or the queries they have.

IPERION HS will be offering several access services to this community and we will need to be able to present the added value of cross-disciplinary research performed through the three platforms. This will be achieved through intensive engagement of international bodies and associations such as ICOMOS (International Council on Monuments and Sites), but also through the more specific communities of BIM (building information modelling) specialists etc. Joint events as well as organisation of joint sessions at annual or biennial conferences of these associations will be carried out in order to develop fruitful collaboration.

Table 2 Institutions to be addressed within T7.4 (*Built Environment Community*)

Bundesanstalt für Materialprüfung (Federal Institute for Materials Testing (D))	BAM	https://www.bam.de/Navigation/EN/Home/home.html
British Institute of Non-Destructive Testing (UK)	BINDT	https://www.bindt.org
Building Research Establishment (UK)	BRE	https://www.bregroup.com/
Climate Heritage Network	CHN	https://climateheritage.org/
International Committee for Documentation of Cultural Heritage	CIPA	https://www.cipaheritagedocumentation.org/
Deutsche Gesellschaft für Zerstörungsfreie Prüfung (D)	DGZfP	https://www.dgzfp.de
Deutsches Nationalkomitee für Denkmalschutz	DNK	http://www.dnk.de/
ECTP - Heritage and Regeneration	ECTP	http://www.ectp.org
European Confederation of Conservator-Restorers' Organisations	ECCO	http://www.ecco-eu.org
European Federation for Construction Chemicals	EFCC	http://www.efcc.eu/
European Federation for Non-Destructive Testing	EFNDT	http://www.efndt.org
European Federation of Natural Stone Industries	EUROROC	www.euroroc.net
European Mineralogical Union	EMU	http://eurominunion.org
Getty Conservation Institute	GCI	https://www.getty.edu/conservation
International Institute for Conservation	IIC	https://www.iiconservation.org
International Council on Monuments and Sites	ICOMOS	https://www.icomos.org/en
International Centre for the Study of the Preservation and Restoration of Cultural Property	ICCROM	https://www.iccrom.org
Sustainable Traditional Buildings Alliance	STBA	https://stbauk.org/home
Verband der Restauratoren Union of Restorers (D)	VDR	https://www.restauratoren.de
International Association for Science and Technology of Building Maintenance and Monuments Preservation WTA	WTA	https://www.wta-international.org/en/
Zentralverband des Handwerks / German Federation of Skilled Crafts	ZDH	https://www.zdh.de/en/

8. Palaeoanthropology and Palaeontology

Purpose

The palaeontology and palaeoanthropology communities represent yet another new group of users for which IPERION HS will represent an attractive offer of scientific facilities. However, there has not been sustained and promoted collaboration in this field in the past, specifically with communities of anthropology, palaeontology, DNA studies, dating and taphonomic studies related to the study of human biological and cultural evolution. This research area is rapidly expanding, specifically with the development of ever better and more accurate techniques to study DNA of past populations and other proteomic and morphological evidence.

Characteristics of the communities

Palaeontologists and paleoanthropologists are more commonly based in university departments than the other communities we are engaging with. They may be more likely to have local links to scientific expertise and may, therefore, already have access to research infrastructures. For example, there are frequent reports in the scientific and public press about paleontological research taking place in synchrotrons³, and members of this community tend to be familiar with complex scientific analysis. Engagement with these communities is more likely to take the form of informing colleagues of the research infrastructures that are available, rather than describing the scientific principles and the uses to which these infrastructures could be put.

General needs

The research infrastructures available in IPERION HS were generally chosen with cultural heritage in mind and may not align with the needs of the palaeontology and palaeoanthropology communities. It is important to determine what this community's needs are and ensure these are fed into future developments of the E-RIHS research infrastructure, for example by liaising with T6.2 (sustainability). Such needs might include, for example, additional research infrastructure used by biologists for advanced analysis of DNA, minerals and proteomics, as well as modern optical, x-ray and electron microscopy techniques.

However, IPERION HS does currently offer new access services that are expected to be valuable to these communities and targeted engagement will be necessary to raise awareness of the facilities on offer such as through joint events and shared conference sessions or presentations with ESHE (European Society for the study of Human Evolution) or The Palaeontological Association. The task will result in a report on palaeoanthropology and palaeontology community research needs that could be addressed using heritage science research facilities (D7.6).

³For example doi:[10.1098/rsfs.2020.0011](https://doi.org/10.1098/rsfs.2020.0011)

Strategies for engagement

STEP 1: Identify National and International Key Experts in university departments and in national and international organisations who can then facilitate contact with key players in the various organisations we wish to engage with.

STEP 2: Engage with the identified Key players and Start a Dialogue – this will involve small groups consisting of the IPERION team with key experts and their international contacts

STEP 3: Identify the Key Areas/Questions to 'Answer' – using the information from STEP 2, determine the research infrastructure needs of the palaeontology and palaeoanthropology communities and determine how to raise awareness of IPERION HS within those communities.

Table 3 Institutions to be addressed within T7.5 (*Palaeoanthropology and Palaeontology*)

Berliner Gesellschaft für Anthropologie, Ethnologie und Urgeschichte	BGAEU	http://www.bgaeu.de/
European Association for the Study of Human Evolution	ESHE	https://www.eshe.eu
Paleontological Association	PALASS	https://www.palass.org
Professional Association for Luminescence & ESR Dating (former <i>Trapped Charge Dating Association</i>)	TCDA	https://led2020burgos.cenieh.es/association
International Union of Prehistoric and Protohistoric Sciences	UISPP	https://www.uispp.org

9. Archaeology

Purpose

The archaeology community, including the related fields of zooarchaeology, archaeobotany, archaeotechnology, geophysics etc., is in many ways a logical extension of the community of users generally already involved in the EU Trans-National access projects in the fields of heritage and conservation sciences. However, the field of archaeology has specific needs and research questions that are related to archaeological sites in the context of development-led change. Such research is thus often related to spatial planning processes. Furthermore, understanding of archaeological context can be used to develop an understanding of the lives of past communities, their social and organisational structures, migration and exchange – all topics relevant to modern social cohesion. Diversity of archaeological evidence is enormous, ranging from whole landscapes and submerged marine environments to microscopic biota. Evidence is often highly scattered and hugely complex computational tools need to be deployed in order to develop a temporal and associational understanding of the components.

Characteristics of the communities

Archaeological scientists generally have a good knowledge and understanding of established and novel techniques and tools that can be used to answer research questions. However, the extent to which archaeological scientists collaborate with field archaeologists and archaeologists based in museums and archives is highly variable, depending on both locality and period of interest. Many archaeologists are aware of the existence of innovative methods of investigation but lack sufficient understanding of how these techniques can be applied to different material remains and which techniques and tools are appropriate to answer specific questions. The different communities within archaeology and heritage science, more generally, interact with each other to varying degrees. Bringing these different groups together to build collaborative communities of practice as part of developing a distributed pan-European research infrastructure, is a key aim.

General needs

- Need to be made aware of the IPERION-HS offer,
- Gain knowledge of the most effective tools and techniques for answering specific research questions,
- Learn who to approach in order to discuss existing research questions,
- Co-create new research questions and collaborative research proposals as part of HS infrastructure development.

Strategies for engagement

STEP 1: In order to raise awareness, we will contact key organisations and individuals within these organisations (see Table 4) offering articles for their newsletters and bulletins and /or presentations to their members on IPERION HS. The IPERION HS co-ordination office will ensure that IPERION HS follows these organisations on Twitter and Facebook in order to start building networks and advertise IPERION HS webinars and the launch of the User Forum (T7.3). These activities will lead to a greater understanding of the tools and techniques available and how they can be used to answer

research questions as well as information on who to go to for advice and help in developing research proposals.

STEP 2: We will develop joint sessions and events with the European Association of Archaeologists, the European Archaeological Council, and other similar associations, in order to develop and grow a strong user base in the future, and to realise greater public benefit. In particular, we will explore the potential for much closer engagement between development-funded archaeologists and the capabilities afforded by heritage science (and by IPERION HS specifically), and investigate user needs and barriers to engagement.

Table 4 Institutions to be addressed within T7.6 (*Archaeology*)

Association for Environmental Archaeology	AEA	https://envarch.net/
Chartered Institute for Archaeologists	CIfA	https://www.archaeologists.net
Deutsche Gesellschaft für Ur- und Frühgeschichte	DGUF	https://www.dguf.de/
Deutscher Verband für Archäologie	DVA	https://www.dvarch.de/
European Association of Archaeologists	EAA	https://www.e-a-a.org
European Archaeology Council	EAC	https://www.europae-archaeologiae-consilium.org
International Medieval Congress	IMC	https://www.imc.leeds.ac.uk/
Palaeopathology Association	PPA	https://paleopathology-association.wildapricot.org/
Association Routes de l' Orient	RDORIENT	https://rdorient.hypotheses.org/lassociation
The Prehistoric Society	PS	http://www.prehistoricsociety.org/
The Roman Society	RS	https://www.romansociety.org/
Society of Archaeological Sciences	SAS	https://socarchsci.org/
Verband der Landesarchäologen	VDL	https://landesarchaeologen.de/

10. Evaluation

We intend to evaluate the success of engagement for all new groups by defining key performance indicators (KPI). These will include:

- Number of requests from new users
- Proportion of requests from new users compared to total number of requests
- Success rate of new users when applying for trans-national access
- Success rate of new users when applying for trans-national access compared to that for established users
- Engagement of new users with social media, webinars etc.
- Number of academic projects (Masters, PhD, published papers etc) resulting from new collaborations

The long-term objective is to develop comprehensible performance indicators for new user groups close to those of already established scientific communities and to closely monitor feedback.

These will be recorded automatically according to access to the IPERION HS websites and by voluntary data acquisition through a questionnaire regarding:

- Membership and affiliations in scientific communities
- Professional background
- Contact ways used to connect with IPERION HS

The Engagement Plan will be updated continually and will be reviewed at the half-way stage of the project in the light of these KPIs.

11. Conclusion

Developing engagement with new user communities must be based on two-way communication. This requires complementary communication at all levels between the parties involved. Diversity and heterogeneity in professional and cultural background and scientific problems faced by new user communities reveal the need to develop a shared professional language and terminology, and acceptance of redundancy in the exchange across disciplinary boundaries. Identifying user's research questions and assessing possibilities and limitations of analytical approaches require an intensive dialogue between all parties. In particular, courage is required in order to admit failures and misunderstandings, and share data and results, even if they are not complete. For many stakeholders in these communities, these are challenging conditions, but if we wish to overcome disciplinary boundaries, we need to embrace these challenges and treat them like opportunities.

The work described in this Deliverable primarily consists of Tasks 7.3-7.6, which are responsible for engagement with each of the four new communities. Other key partners within IPERION HS are Task 7.2 (responsible for the User Forum, which will include the development of targeted webinars), Task 6.2 (sustainability) and WP8 (Central support), especially Task 8.3 (Communication).

D7.6 Report on engagement with user communities and on user research needs will assess the success of this communication plan and the participation of new user groups (Tasks 7.3-7.6).